

EOMORES

D3.3 EO based processors and products

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730066.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	730066	Acronym	EOMORES	
Full Title	Earth Observation-Based Services For Monitoring And Reporting Of Ecological Status			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2016: Downstream applications			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	01/12/2016	Duration	36 months	
Project URL	http://eomores-h2020.eu			
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION			
Project Coordinator	Water Insight BV			
Deliverable	D3.3 EO based processors and products			
Work Package	WP3 EO component			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M10	Actual	M10
Nature	R – Report		Dissemination Level	P - Public
Lead Beneficiary	WI			
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Reviewer(s)	Reviewers (WI)			
Keywords	Satellite data, image processing, algorithms, products			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	2017-09-01	Template		Water Insight
1.1	2018-09-11	Version for the partners	Compilation of the main section	CNR
1.2	2018-09-11	Version edited by the partners	Compilation of all sections and final editing	CNR, PML, TO, WI, KU, SYKE
1.3	2018-09-23	Version ready for the internal review	Final revision	WI

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I. List of Acronyms and Symbols

AATSR: Advanced Along Track Scanning Radiometer
AOP: apparent optical properties
AVHRR: Advanced very-high-resolution radiometer
C2RCC: Case-2 Regional / Coast Colour
CDOM: Colored Dissolved Organic Matter
Chl-a: Chlorophyll-a
Ci: Concentration of the i-water components
CZCS: Coastal Zone Color Scanner
EO: Earth Observation
IOP: inherent optical properties
Kd: downwelling diffuse attenuation coefficient
LSWT: Lake surface water temperature
MCI: Maximum Chlorophyll Index
MERIS: MEdium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer
MODIS: Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MSI: Multispectral Instrument
MSL: Mean Sea Level
NDAVI: Normalized Difference Aquatic Vegetation Index
NN: Neural Network
OLCI: Ocean and Land Colour Instrument
OWT: optical water type
PC: Phycocyanin
RMSE: Root Mean Squared Error
Rrs: Remote Sensing Reflectance
SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar
SeaWiFS: Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
SLSTR: Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SPM: Suspended Particulate Matter
SRF: Spectral Response function
TOA: Top of Atmosphere
TCHL: Total Chlorophyll
TSM: Total Suspended Matter
Vis: Vegetation Indices
VIIRS: Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite
WAVI: Water Adjusted Vegetation Index
WFD: Water Framework Directive
YS: Yellow Substance
6SV: Second Simulation of the Satellite Signal in the Solar Spectrum

II. Abstract

In recent years satellite water quality information have been used for several purposes, such as: 1) regular and specific monitoring, 2) matters that require Near Real Time information (e.g. when cyanobacterial blooms are threatening the swimming water quality) and 3) for the spatial optimisation of monitoring networks. To the aim, image processing chains need to be set up to transform the radiance recorded by satellite sensors into information on water quality, such as the concentrations of water constituents, the physical values on water surface temperature or maps depicting e.g. the spatial extent of aquatic vegetation. Despite these techniques have been developed since about three decades, there are still ongoing developments to produce accurate and consistent products across all water bodies.

This is particularly the case for EOMORES, whose target lakes include a wide range of water types. Moreover, as EOMORES makes use of the latest generation of satellite sensors, consolidated image processing techniques need to be adapted according to the resolutions and spectral bands of these newest sensors. This is especially relevant for Sentinel-2 MSI, since for Sentinel-3 OLCI most of the developments are based on its precursor MERIS on Envisat (2002-2012).

This document hence illustrates the image processing chain that have been adapted to produce relevant water quality information for the EOMORES study sites. A first section is dedicated to the description of the methods while the last part describes how the processors have been applied to produce maps (both of the past and recent years, including 2018) of water quality. The selected processors are now being used to set up the operational EOMORES service according to WP6.

III. Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems are an essential renewable resource for mankind and the environment; it plays a key role in the European and world-wide economy since it is exploited for civil (drinking water supply, irrigation, transportation), industrial (processing and cooling, energy production, fishery) and recreational purposes. Within this frame, Earth Observation (EO) provide relevant information to monitor water quality as well as to estimate biophysical parameters. Interested users are both institutional and private. Institutional users include environment agencies, water management authorities and port authorities. Private users include agriculture, forestry, aquaculture, dredging companies and drinking water companies. Fishery and recreation industries are also interested, from the water quality and clarity as well as benthic habitat point of view.

Long term, consistently implemented water quality monitoring programs are critical in order to detect changes in water quality. They are required to monitor the effects of past and ongoing management programs and to monitor the effects of continuing anthropogenic influences. Ultimately, the monitoring programs are needed to implement national, European, international directives and conventions put in place to know how water quality is not deteriorating. A clear example comes from the Water Framework Directive (WFD) of the European Commission (Directive 2000/60/EC, 2000) that is the major reference in Europe to guide efforts for attaining a sustainable aquatic environment in the years to come.

Within EMORES, remote sensing of water quality has been proposed as an operational means to support the needs of multiple users who are interested in WFD monitoring as well as to more specific interest such as ecological insights, plume monitoring, and bathing water warnings.

When deterioration of lake water quality is caused by optically active substances, the effect of these changes can be observed with optical remote sensing instruments. In general, the parameters that have been identified in literature as detectable by modern satellites are:

- Green algae pigments mainly as Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) or as the sum of Chl-a and Phaeopigments (Total Chlorophyll or TCHL). Chl-a or TCHL is used as a proxy of phytoplankton biomass.
- Total Suspended Matter (TSM) (also referred to as SPM or suspended particulate matter) which is placed in suspension by wind-wave stirring of shallow waters and is a tracer for inflowing pollutants.
- Coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), commonly called Yellow Substance (YS).
- The diffused attenuation (K_d) as measure for the water transparency.
- The cyanobacterial pigment phycocyanin (PC).

Since the 1980s, satellite remote sensing represents an opportunity for synoptic and multitemporal viewing of water quality of lakes. Strengths of remote sensing methods for lake monitoring are the good spatial and temporal coverage, compared to other monitoring methods, and the possibility to monitor many lakes simultaneously including those that cannot be covered by national monitoring programs. The improved temporal, spatial and radiometric resolutions provide valuable information on seasonal variability of water quality and on the spatial variability of optical water constituents.

One of the challenges for lake remote sensing (as compared to ocean color) is that the ranges of concentrations are extremely wide: lakes might have Chl-a levels ranging between $< 0.5 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ to

over 100 mg m^{-3} . Some lakes are very shallow and are very sensitive to resuspension by wind forcing, resulting in high sediment loads up to 30 g m^{-3} . Many lakes and basins regularly suffer from cyanobacterial blooms while oligotrophic Nordic lakes may feature very high CDOM concentrations while alpine oligotrophic lakes may have very low CDOM values.

Another challenge is then facing the atmospheric effects. Light received by a passive observing remote sensor goes through the Earth's atmosphere twice from the Sun to the Earth's surface and from the surface to the sensor before it reaches the sensor. As such, the light received at the sensor is invariably affected by absorption and scattering by gaseous molecules and particulate matter in the atmosphere. The process of correcting for the atmospheric effects and retrieving the reflectance of a target on the Earth's surface is called atmospheric correction. The atmospheric effect on the radiance received by a remote sensor is significantly large over water bodies because water is highly absorptive and contributes to only 20% or less of the total at sensor radiance (e.g., Hovis and Leung, 1977). Correcting for these atmospheric effects is an essential prerequisite to retrieving accurate estimates of water-leaving radiance, which is the basis for deriving quantitative estimates of biophysical parameters from remotely sensed data.

Since the launch of the first ocean color sensor, the Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS), in 1978, numerous algorithms have been developed to correct for atmospheric effects on remotely sensed data from water. Robust atmospheric correction algorithms have been developed for open ocean waters (e.g., Gordon and Wang, 1994), which have proven successful for correcting data from multispectral ocean color sensors such as MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), the Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS), and the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS). Then, since the size of many lakes is too small for being captured by ocean color sensors, the developments of algorithms has been in the filed were also driven by land satellite missions (mainly Landsat) and imaging spectrometry e.g. Lindell et al. (1999).

In any case, extending these algorithms to inland waters is not a simple, straightforward transition due to a number of factors that invalidate some basic assumptions inherent in these algorithms. The factors include:

- proximity to terrestrial sources of atmospheric pollution, which results in an optically heterogeneous atmosphere that is difficult to model;
- adjacency effects from neighboring land pixels, which is especially significant in cases of a raised, undulating topography around the water body;
- non-negligible reflectance of water in the near-infrared region due to high sediment concentrations in inland waters (caused by, for example, agricultural and industrial discharge from terrestrial sources, surface and sub-surface runoff, wind-driven resuspension of sediments, and sediment influx from landslides and shoreline erosion), which makes it difficult to accurately estimate and remove the effect of atmospheric aerosol contribution on the received signal;
- variations in the altitude of inland water surface from the Mean Sea Level (MSL), which introduces uncertainties in the estimates of aerosol content in the atmospheric column above the water.

III.1. Scope

The scope of this document is to illustrate the processors of satellite data that have been adopted within EOMORES to operationally generate user products depicting the concentration of water quality parameters. A main section is dedicated to the retrieval of water leaving reflectance and concentration of water quality parameters. Other minor sections show: 1) how thermal data are used to produce for assessing water surface temperature and 2) how radar images might support the detection of cyanobacteria scum at the surface.

IV. Approach

Most of the challenges in inland and coastal water observations are due to their optical complexity. These aquatic ecosystems can be a mixture of optically shallow and optically deep waters, with gradients of clear to turbid and oligotrophic to hypertrophic productive waters and varying bottom visibility with and without macrophytes. For example, a lake receives and recycles organic and inorganic substances from within the lake, from its watershed and beyond (atmospheric deposition). Hence, a large range in optical absorption and backscattering resulting in high optical variability can be found among and within lakes, estuaries and coastal waters. This poses a challenge for bio-optical algorithms applied to optical remote sensing for water quality monitoring applications. Another challenge is performing atmospheric corrections over such variable aquatic ecosystems as their complexity requires different approaches than those for land and ocean applications.

To convert EO data into water quality parameters different techniques have been developed in the last decades. These techniques all assume that pre-processing steps such as acquiring the images from data providers, ingestion of data into a system and subsetting of data according to the site are done as a common implicit part of the processing (Figure 1). Similarly, processing techniques also include the need to make the imagery geocoded into a uniform geo-referenced systems and to take into account the radiometric features of data, so that the input data are all provided in physical units of radiance. By assuming that such steps are rather common, the document focuses on the basic, most important steps needed to convert radiance data at satellite level (Level 1) into bio-geophysical products at the ground (Level 2).

Figure 1 Overview of processing steps adopted in EOMORES to obtain EO products; this document is focused on the conversion of satellite data (Level 1) into water quality parameters (Level 2)

These steps basically include advanced techniques that have been developed and/or tested by project partners in recent years for assessing water quality from the latest generation of optical satellite data such as Sentinel-3 OLCI and Sentinel-2 MSI. In particular we used a series of methods that have been demonstrated to provide accurate mapping of water quality in the EOMORES sites (cf. Del 5.2).

The methods that are accurately described in the following sections are intended to both correct the atmospheric effects and to retrieve the concentrations of water quality parameters. The selected processors first allow estimating the Remote Sensing Reflectance (R_{rs}) at the water surface. A series of algorithms is then needed to infer the concentrations of water components C_i (where i mostly stays for Chl-a, SPM, and CDOM). More in particular, POLYMER and 6SV provide R_{rs} , while ACOLITE and C2RCC already have been designed to estimate C_i and IOPs, according to predefined algorithms as described in the next section.

To parametrise the atmospheric parameters (e.g. aerosol optical depth, ratio of direct/diffuse irradiance) the models make different assumptions but basically two groups are identified: 1) those that take ancillary information of atmospheric optical properties (e.g. from AERONET, WISPSStations, radiosonde profiles); and those that infer these information from imagery data (e.g. ACOLITE).

Figure 2 Overview of processors adopted in EOMORES to obtain the products describing water quality

V. EO processors adopted in the project

V.1. Polymer

POLYMER (POLYnomial based algorithm applied to MERIS, Steinmetz et al., 2011), developed by HYGEOS is an algorithm for multi-sensor atmospheric correction, used in the frame of the Ocean Colour Climate change Initiative and in operational services since 2008. It includes a water model inside the process of atmospheric correction dealing at the same time with issues due to glint, absorbing aerosols and adjacency effects. The strength of POLYMER is due to the fact that it takes into account the whole spectrum to model atmospheric contribution.

The signal is first corrected for the effect of ozone transmission, the Rayleigh scattering and a first guess of the glint contribution $\rho_{\text{mol+gli}}(\lambda, V_{\text{wind}})$, estimated as in Cox and Munk (1954), using the

wind speed values provided by ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts): the total contribution of Rayleigh scattering, the sun glint and the coupling between Rayleigh scattering and sun glint is calculated with the Successive Order of Scattering radiative transfer code SOS and stored in look-up tables.

$$\rho'(\lambda) = \frac{\rho_{TOA}(\lambda)}{t_{oz}} - \rho_{mol+gli}(\lambda, V_{wind})$$

where t_{oz} is the ozone transmission, depending on the total ozone concentration obtained from ECMWF data. The atmosphere contribution and the residual sun glint are then modelled as a polynomial with three terms:

$$\rho_{ag}(\lambda) \approx T_0(\lambda)c_0 + c_1\lambda^{-1} + c_2\lambda^{-4}$$

where $T_0(\lambda)$ is the transmission factor

$$T_0(\lambda) \approx e^{-\tau_m(\lambda) \left(1 - 0.5 e^{-\frac{\rho_{gli}}{\rho_{gli,0}}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\mu_s} + \frac{1}{\mu_v} \right)}$$

where μ_s and μ_v are the cosines of the solar and view zenith angles, and τ_m is the Rayleigh optical thickness: $\tau_m(\lambda) \approx 0.00877\lambda - 4.05$. ρ_{gli} is the glint contribution estimated at first step and $\rho_{gli,0}$ is the threshold equal to 2% used to switch between the direct (in the sun glint areas, where $\rho_{gli} > \rho_{gli,0}$) and diffuse (outside sun glint areas, where $\rho_{gli} < \rho_{gli,0}$) transmission factors.

A second model, a bio-optical water reflectance model, is then used to estimate water reflectance just above the surface from the chlorophyll concentration [chl] and the backscattering coefficient of non-co-varying particles $bb_{NC}(\lambda)$ as in Morel (1988) and Morel and Maritorena (2001):

$$\rho_{wmod}^+([chl], b_{bNC}, \lambda) = \begin{cases} \rho_{wMM}^+([chl], b_{bNC}, \lambda) & \lambda < 700 \text{ nm} \\ \frac{\rho_{wS}^+(\lambda) \rho_{wMM}^+([chl], b_{bNC}, 700 \text{ nm})}{\rho_{wS}^+(700 \text{ nm})} & \lambda \geq 700 \text{ nm} \end{cases}$$

where

$$\rho_{wMM}^+([chl], b_{bNC}, \lambda) = 0.544 \rho_{wmod}^-([chl], bb_{NC}, \lambda) = f \frac{0.5b_w(\lambda) + b_{bp}(\lambda) + b_{bNC}(\lambda)}{a(\lambda)}$$

with $b_w(\lambda)$, $b_{bp}(\lambda)$, and $b_{bNC}(\lambda)$ being the scattering coefficient of pure water multiplied by a factor 1.3 for taking into account salinity effects, and the backscattering coefficients of particles and of non-covarying particles, respectively. $a(\lambda)$ is total absorption. The model is extended from 700 nm to 900 nm, by using the similarity spectrum for turbid waters (Ruddick et al., 2006).

The conversion to reflectance above the surface is done by assuming that the radiance in-water is Lambertian.

The estimate of the polynomial parameters (c_0 , c_1 , and c_2), [chl], and b_{bNC} are estimated through the spectral matching between water reflectance estimated by the two different models. Starting from a starting couple of values ([chl], b_{bNC}), an iterative process calculates $\rho_{wmod}^+(\lambda)$, then used to retrieve $\rho_{ag}(\lambda)$ as the difference between $\rho'(\lambda)$ and $t(\lambda)\rho_{wmod}^+(\lambda)$.

The tuple (c_0 , c_1 , and c_2), is estimated through polynomial fit to $\rho_{ag}(\lambda)$. The RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) of this fit is thus evaluated along the spectrum and used as cost function. The final

values of $([chl], b_{bNC})$ are obtained by a n-dimensional iterative minimization technique of the cost function, using a simplex method as described in Nelder and Mead (1965). At the end of the process, $\rho_w(\lambda)$ is finally obtained as:

$$\rho_w(\lambda) = \frac{\rho'(\lambda) - T_0(\lambda)c_0 + c_1\lambda^{-1} + c_2\lambda^{-4}}{t(\lambda)}$$

As output, POLYMER provides both ρ_w , from which Rrs is obtained dividing by π , glint reflectance.

V.2. 6SV

The 6SV code (Second Simulation of the Satellite Signal in the Solar Spectrum – Vector, Vermote et al., 1997) is the vector version of 6S, a basic Radiative Transfer code used for calculation of lookup tables in the MODIS atmospheric correction algorithm, based on the approximations and implementation of the successive order of scattering (SOS) algorithm. 6S simulates the atmospheric radiative transfer in the 400-2500 nm spectral range at a spectral resolution of 2.5 nm. It was used in this thesis through an interface realised by CNR-IREA (Figure 3) to include as input to 6SV also microphysical properties of aerosols as provided by AERONET stations close to study areas (example of Lake Garda in Figure 4), and specific sensors Spectral Response function (SRF).

Figure 3 Overview of the GUI developed by CNR-IREA to run the 6SV

Figure 4 AERONET data measured from AERONET site of Lake Garda in September 2018

6SV allows in fact to simulate for each defined band the radiative transfer, according to the geometry of the acquisition and the atmospheric condition over the target area. Columnar ozone and water vapour concentrations can be defined through both predefined models as in Table 1, or user defined values. The gaseous transmission is calculated from a random exponential band model: Goody and Yung (1996) model is used for water vapour and Malkmus (1997) model for Oxygen, Ozone, Carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. 6SV assumes that all gases apart from water vapour and ozone are uniformly mixed within the atmosphere and of constant density over time (Proud et al., 2010). Also aerosol type can be defined both through predefined models, characterized by different percentage of four different components (dust-like, water-soluble, oceanic, and soot), which can be also defined by the user. In addition, it allows to describe aerosol through microphysical properties (particles size distribution and Complex Refractive Index, $m = n - ik$, which describes scattering and absorption properties of atmospheric particulate matters) as estimated through sunphotometers measurements.

Table 1 Atmospheric profiles available for 6SV parametrization

Code	Atmospheric profile	Water Vapour (g/cm ²)	Ozone (cm-atm)
0	No gaseous absorption	0	0
1	Tropical	4.120	0.247
2	Mid-latitude Summer	2.930	0.319
3	Mid-latitude Winter	0.853	0.395
4	Subarctic Summer	2.100	0.480
5	Subarctic Winter	0.419	0.480
6	US standard 62	1.420	0.344

Finally, aerosol load can be described both through visibility values or Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT) at 550 nm.

As output, for each band λ , 6SV provides among other the integrated values of global, water, ozone, CO₂, oxygen, NO₂, CH₄, and CO gaseous transmittance, total, Rayleigh, and aerosol scattering transmittance, direct, diffuse and environmental irradiance. In addition, it provides the three coefficients $x_a(\lambda)$, $x_b(\lambda)$, and $x_c(\lambda)$ applicable to obtain water reflectance ρ_w from Radiance at

Top of Atmosphere L_{toa} . For each site, target elevation was accounted for, and a Lambertian ground surface was assumed.

$$\rho_w(\lambda) = \frac{L_{toa}(\lambda) x_a(\lambda) - x_b(\lambda)}{1 + x_c(\lambda) (L_{toa}(\lambda) x_a(\lambda) - x_b(\lambda))}$$

V.3. C2RCC

C2RCC (Brockmann et al., 2016) is a JAVA application that can be run within the SNAP processing toolbox (<http://step.esa.int/main/toolboxes/snap>). C2RCC is a processor based on Neural Network (NN) techniques, originally developed by Doerffer and Schiller (2007, 2008) as *Case 2 Regional* processor and then improved through the CoastColour (www.coastcolour.org) project, available for L8-OLI, S2-MSI, and S3-OLCI.

It uses, for NN training, a large database of radiative transfer simulations of water leaving radiances and TOA radiances, to perform the inversion of spectrum for the atmospheric correction, to determine the water leaving radiance from the TOA radiances, and inherent optical properties of the water body, in a coupled system of an in-water and an atmospheric radiative transfer modelling.

The in-water modelling is performed using the *Hydrolight* model (Mobley and Sundman, 2013), parametrized through a bio-optical model with five components for scattering and absorption, defined at 443 nm: pigment absorption (*apig*), detritus absorption (*adet*), gelbstoff absorption (*agelb*), a white scatterer for calcareous sediments (*bwhit*), and a typical sediment scatterer (*btsm*). *Apig* is used as a proxy of chl-a concentration, *bwhit* and *btsm* for TSM concentration, to which IOPs are converted through scaling factors.

Figure 5 Schematic of the C2RCC development process (from Brockmann et al., 2016)

A careful characterisation of optically complex waters through its inherent optical properties (IOP) as well as of coastal atmospheres is used to parameterize radiative transfer models for the water body and the atmosphere. Covariances between the water constituents are taken into account and a large database of reflectances at the water surface is calculated. These reflectances are further used as lower boundary condition for the radiative transfer calculation in the atmosphere and finally a database of ~5 million cases is generated (this is the basis for training NNs). A schematic overview is given in Figure 5.

Within EOMORES, C2RCC is used for the alternative atmospheric correction over Case-2 waters, for processing Sentinel-3 OLCI, Sentinel2A&b and Landsat-8 OLI.

V.4. ACOLITE

ACOLITE bundles the atmospheric correction algorithms and processing software developed at RBINS for aquatic applications of Landsat (5/7/8) and Sentinel-2 (A/B) satellite data. ACOLITE performs both the atmospheric correction and can output several parameters derived from water reflectances (Figure 6). Red-Green-Blue composites and PNG maps can also be generated. ACOLITE was originally implemented in IDL (2014-2017), and has been translated into Python (2018). The original IDL implementation is no longer supported or developed.

Figure 6 Overview of the GUI developed by RBINS for ACOLITE (similar examples for earlier/newer versions)

ACOLITE Python includes several algorithms for the retrieval of water quality parameters such as chl-a, turbidity, SPM and IOPs. The L2R file is used as an input and an L2W file is generated containing the requested datasets. The L2W file will be used to generate maps from the parameters if requested.

V.5. Algorithms for water quality parameters from Rrs data

Various algorithms exist to derive water quality parameters in both optically deep and optically shallow waters based on the relation between remote sensing reflectance, concentration and IOPs of water components, and bottom albedo. The approaches that are used to invert these relations, typically distinguish between empirical and analytical algorithms (Odermatt et al. 2012).

In many applications (e.g., TSM, Turbidity, Chl-a) the concentrations of water components are often retrieved by empirical or semi-empirical algorithms. They make use of single band, band ratio or band difference positioned at wavelengths where remote sensing reflectance is sensitive to variation

of water components. The single band algorithms, such as for instance Nechad et al. (2010) for TSM and turbidity, have a sound theoretical background and perform well in a variety of coastal and inland waters; for waters with large variety in concentrations an additional switching has been proposed between several bands at longer wavelengths (Shen et al. 2010; Dogliotti et al. 2015). However, single band algorithms are generally sensitive to the variability in reflectance due to influences of other water constituents, the natural variability in the IOPs and to errors in the atmospheric correction (e.g., Sterckx et al. 2007). To overcome this issue, as well as to account for changes in the concentrations of water constituents and in the spectral shape of their IOPs, several band ratio and band difference models have been proposed for different variables. Gitelson et al. (2007) used band ratios of the value of signal at the secondary Chl-a absorption maximum (at around 675 nm) to that at adjacent spectral bands not affected by phytoplankton absorption. These algorithms are typically applicable to Chl-a concentrations above $\sim 10 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$. As the backscattering coefficient has a relatively flat spectral signature, Doxaran et al. (2003) used red-to-green and near-infrared-(NIR)-to-red band ratios for estimating TSM and turbidity. In this case, band ratio algorithms demonstrate reduced effects of variable sediment types and become less sensitive to illumination conditions. Restricted to certain water types in which CDOM dominates absorption in the blue (i.e. high CDOM and low Chl-a) and in which the NIR is not affected much by TSM, CDOM has been estimated with band ratios of blue and NIR bands (Kutser et al. 2005).

Other algorithm approaches are based on the spectral inversion of analytical bio-optical models, such as the one presented in the sections above, and of numerical radiative transfer models (e.g., Hydrolight, Mobley 1994). The models are inverted through neural networks (e.g., Doerffer and Schiller 2007; Schroeder et al. 2007), use of Look Up Tables (Salem et al. 2017), matrix inversion (e.g., Brando and Dekker 2003), quasi-analytical approaches (e.g., Lee et al. 2002) or curve fitting techniques (e.g., Keller 2001) using the different spectral bands available. These approaches provide a robust mechanism for inverting reflectance into IOPs and water quality parameters through a combination of radiative transfer theory and a level of empiricism due to the need for “a priori” SIOP parametrisation (Werdell et al. 2013).

VI. Thermal infrared data

Water surface temperature is the result of the energy balance at the water surface and heat transport mechanisms within the water body. It is an important water quality parameter related to biodiversity in lakes and its knowledge is needed to characterize processes at the water surface.

Lake surface water temperature (LSWT) reflects meteorological and climatological forcing more than any other physical lake parameter. It is strongly related to the mean temperature of the upper stratum, which plays an important role in lake’s biology depending, among other factors, on the dynamics of phytoplankton. In particular in polymictic lakes, with shallow bottoms and continuous mixing of water layers, but also in monomictic deep lakes, where surface temperatures might be related to the water stratification and the thermocline structure as suggested (Dessi et al. 2011). In particular, water temperature is one of the most important parameters determining ecological conditions in lakes, because it influences water chemistry as well as biological processes inside of a lake.

Since three decades, remote sensing provides continuous data for observing spatial and temporal variation of lake surface temperatures worldwide. Most of the studies have been based on

moderate spatial resolution sensors (pixel size of about 1 km), such as AVHRR, MODIS, ATSR, ATSR-2 and AATSR (e.g. Reinart and Reinhold, 2008), which provides a daily-based frequency of monitoring. Nevertheless, the use of these sensors in smaller lakes is challenging because their spatial resolution is too coarse. In this case, Landsat, a joint NASA/USGS program providing the longest continuous space-based record of Earth's land in existence, represents the main source of data (pixel size in the order of 100 m) (Wloczyk et al. 2006) yet its poorer revisiting time (16 days).

Within EOMORES the Level2 products from Sentinel 3 SLSTR and Aqua MODIS, already delivered by the agencies in geocoded physical values of LSWT, with masks for clouds, have been directly provided to the users.

VII. EO processors for non-operational products

VII.1. Aquatic vegetation

VII.1.1. Emerging macrophytes

Remote sensing applications for mapping and studying vegetation status and its dynamics, from local to global scales, make large use of approaches based on vegetation indices (VIs), for their flexibility, easiness of use and cross-platform consistency. The use of VIs relies on the identification of key spectral wavebands, related to specific physiological and structural characteristics of plants, which are combined into indices implemented in empirical and semi-empirical approaches (Gitelson and Merzlyak, 1996; Haboudane et al., 2004).

Recently, spectral VIs specifically optimized for aquatic vegetation have been designed and tested using broadband spectral ranges currently available for a vast group of sensors: i.e. the Normalized Difference Aquatic Vegetation Index (NDAVI, Villa et al., 2013; Villa et al., 2014a) and the Water Adjusted Vegetation Index (WAVI; Villa et al., 2014a). They are based on some peculiar spectral characteristics of aquatic vegetation.

NDAVI and WAVI are following the simple and broadly tested normalized differencing approach (McFeeters, 1996; Jiang et al., 2008) and come as adaptations of the common NDVI and its derivations, where the vegetation background is usually composed of water rather than soil. The Normalized Difference Aquatic Vegetation Index (NDAVI) exploits the visible shortwave range commonly defined as blue natural color range (approximately centered at 480 nm), and the near infrared range (approximately centered at 800-850 nm). NDAVI is formulated as:

$$NDAVI = \frac{\rho(780 - 800) - \rho(480 - 510)}{\rho(780 - 800) + \rho(480 - 510)}$$

WAVI includes a correction for background effect, and is derived from NDAVI the same way as soil adjusted vegetation index (SAVI) is derived from NDVI, by the introduction of a correction factor to adjust the influence of vegetation background (Huete, 1988). WAVI is formulated as:

$$WAVI = 1.5 \frac{\rho(780-800) - \rho(480-510)}{\rho(780-800) + \rho(480-510) + 0.5}$$

VII.1.2. Submerged macrophytes

The main recent development in submerged vegetation remote sensing algorithms is that of physics-based model inversion approaches. These methods work by establishing a forward model for the remote sensing reflectance R_{rs} based on the depth, optical properties of the water and bottom type. The majority of methods are based on a set of equations derived by Lee et al (1998; 1999) which can be represented by the following function

$$R_{rs}(\lambda) \approx f(P, G, X, H, R(\lambda), \lambda)$$

Where P , G , X represent the amount of phytoplankton, dissolved organic matter (CDOM) and particulate backscatter, H is the depth and $R(\lambda)$ is the bottom type. Finding the best match between a modelled spectra and the pixel reflectance (by successive approximation or look-up tables) provides an estimate for all the parameters, including the depth and bottom type in each pixel (Figure 7). The method can therefore accommodate pixel-to-pixel variation in water optical properties.

Although many variants of this approach have been produced (Dekker et al. 2012) they are based on the same underlying equations: despite differences in the details their fundamental performance should be similar. Within EOMORES a reference code for this approach is BOMBER (Giardino et al. 2012).

Figure 7 Sentinel-2 MSI data from southern part of Lake Garda, Italy, acquired on the 3rd July 2017. From left to right: a pseudo-true-colour composite; bottom depth; submerged vegetation map to 10 m depth (the map contains main bottom cover classes of sand (b0, blue), submersed benthic vegetation (b1, red) such as *Chara* sp., and submersed tall vegetation (b2, green) such as *Vallisneria spiralis*; black areas in the map are masked as optically deep water areas.

VII.2. Optical & SAR integration

Even if this is obvious, clouds might significantly hinder the use of optical data. To show the impact of clouds, the assessment of cloudiness from Mercury et al (2015), who build a composite of MODIS-Terra 2001–2011 providing the percent cloudiness for the entire 10-year period globally, has been exploited for the EOMORES lakes. It obviously appeared (Figure 8) that northern Europe appears more cloudy than southern regions with Lake Trasimeno (Italy) being the less affected by cloudiness. The analysis according to seasons shows (Figure 9) how summer months (July through September) offer the highest chance to have EO optical cloud-free data for observing the all EOMORES targets except those in UK, Scotland where all seasons remain very challenging.

Figure 8 Cloudiness (with 0=100% cloud-free and 100=100% cloud cover) derived from composite of 2001–2010 data of Mercury et al., 2012

Figure 9 Cloudiness (with 0=100% cloud-free and 100=100% cloud cover) derived from composite of 2001–2010 data of Mercury et al., 2012. For (JFM) January through March, (AMJ) April through June, (JAS) July through September, and (OND) October through December

Within the project, the use of SAR data to augment the revisiting time of optical data in case of clouds is investigated for the potentiality of radar data in detecting surface scum due to important cyanobacterial blooms. To test the SAR sensitivity a selection of case studies was done searching those days in which:

- both radar and optical images are available,
- the optical image shows some scum phenomena,
- the radar images is acquired in daytime.

At this stage we have considered only Sentinel-2 as optical sensor and the Kaunas damp, the Curonia lagoon, the Taihu and the Chaohu lake as inland water to analyze.

It is well known that Sentinel-1 image intensity is disturbed by additive thermal noise particularly in cross-polarization channel. This thermal noise can be often neglected in many applications, but has serious impact for inland waters applications. The first step of the Sentinel-1 image analysis is therefore applying the noise vectors provided by ESA for the thermal noise subtraction. As optional second step, when is needed, consecutive Sentinel-1 images are merged. The processed SAR data is then calibrated to be converted into measurements of radar back scatter (the so called σ_0) and finally re-projected with an ellipsoid correction. The Sentinel-1 product obtained with this procedure is stacked with the optical image acquired in the same day and analyzed. A CMOD model (which describes the relationship between microwave backscatter, local incidence angle, relative wind direction and wind speed at 10 m height above the mean sea level) is used to have an estimation of the clear water σ_0 that can be compared with the observed σ_0 . First results suggest that a localized attenuation of the microwave backscatter signal can reveal the presence of scum.

VIII. EO products generation

In order to report the status on EO product generation and reporting, a country-based organisation is adopted. In fact, within EOMORES, there are six countries: Estonia, Finland, Italy, Lithuania, The Netherlands and the UK, spanning a wide range of latitudes (from 43° N to up 65°N) and ecoregions (from Mediterranean to Boreal) (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Overview of the States where the EOMORES sites are located, the plot shows the variability of R_{rs} that can be met in different water bodies under investigation

This gradient has an impact on lake/catchment features (Spyrakos et al. 2017 and Eleveld et al. 2017) so that different water types are found in the project. Such a variability has then an impact on the retrieval of water quality parameters that within the project is considered by adopting the best performing EO processor as follows.

As a preliminary step (i.e. to have data), all imagery data of the most used sensors were gathered from the following sources:

- Sentinel-2A/B MSI L1C were downloaded via Copernicus Open Access Hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>).
- Sentinel-3A OLCI L1B Full Resolution (300 m) images were downloaded via Copernicus Online Data Access CODA (<https://codata.eumetsat.int/#/home>).
- L8 OLI images were downloaded from USGS (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). OLI L1 images were downloaded via glovis (<https://glovis.usgs.gov/>).

Apart for Caminos, most of the Sentinel 2 and 3 pre-processing such as subsetting and resampling of data was performed in SNAP-toolbox. In case of other sensors (e.g. MODIS), the data source is provided in the sections below according to the need of using these data to meet user requirements.

VIII.1. Estonia

Sentinel-3A OLCI and Sentinel-2A/B MSI L1C were processed with SNAP for geocoding, subsetting and resampling. Based on the lake type and the end-user requirements, different products were generated from EO data either from L1 or L2 S3/OLCI and S2/MSI products. For deriving phytoplankton related parameters (chl a, phytoplankton biomass and cyanobacterial biomass) over eutrophic lakes, mainly L1 data is used. For transparency (either expressed as $K_d(490)$ or Secchi depth), the Rrs and IOPs were used from the C2RCC processed data.

- Phytoplankton: over large eutrophic lakes, the chl a was derived from L1 data where the Maximum Chlorophyll Index (MCI) developed by Gower et al. 2008 was applied and the chl-a (Figure 11), phytoplankton biomass (Figure 10) and cyanobacterial biomass were derived based on the empirical relationships shown in Alikas et al. 2010.

Figure 11 S3/OLCI based monthly means of Chl a in L.Peipsi and in L. Vörtsjärv in 2016

Figure 12 S3/OLCI based monthly means of phytoplankton biomass in L.Peipsi and in L. Vörtsjärv in 2016

For smaller lakes, potentially monitored by S2/MSI the Three-Band NIR-Red model algorithm (Gitelson et al. 2003) has been used for deriving chl-a (Figure 13) according to:

$$chl - a \propto \left[\frac{1}{Rrs(665)} - \frac{1}{Rrs(705)} \right] * Rrs(783)$$

Figure 13 Chl a time series in L. Vörtsjärv from S2/MSI data

- Transparency as $K_d(490)$: input data was C2RCC processed L2 Rrs products where based on the bands at 490, 560, 709 nm, $K_d(490)$ is calculated after Alikas et al 2015.
- Transparency as Secchi depth: input data is C2RCC processed L2 products. Secchi depth is calculated after Alikas et al. 2017 where the inputs to the algorithms are $K_d(490)$, total beam attenuation coefficient $c(\lambda)$ and Rrs at 560nm. $K_d(\lambda)$ and $c(\lambda)$ are derived after Alikas et al. 2015. Example of the product is given in Figure 12.

Figure 14 Monthly means of Secchi depth in L. Peipsi and in L. Võrtsjärv in 2016

VIII.2. Finland

SYKE water quality estimates for lakes and coastal waters are turbidity, Secchi disk depth, chl-a and absorption coefficient of CDOM (aCDOM) at wavelength 400nm. In addition, SST is produced for the Baltic Sea and largest Finnish lakes during April - October. OLCI-based algae bloom maps covering the whole Baltic Sea are produced during the cyanobacteria period (end of June to the beginning of September). High resolution algae bloom maps are produced for the coastal waters of Finland and central Baltic Sea. Other products than SST are based on regionally calibrated outputs of C2RCC and C2X processors. SYKE produces four types of EO products:

- image products (cf. Figure 17)
- statistics and time series for WFD water bodies (cf. Figure 18)
- time series of water quality parameters at reference stations (cf. Figure 19)
- Spatial representativeness analysis EO product.

All three product types for each water quality parameter follow the same algorithm definitions, but they are derived separately using CalFin (a massive parallel processing system of SYKE). Image products are produced for turbidity, Secchi disk depth and aCDOM. Likewise to the other parameters, statistics of Chl-a are produced for WFD water bodies using S2A-MSI and S2B-MSI instruments and later on also using OLCI.

The conversion between IOPs and water quality parameters is done through scaling factors, adjusted to fit the specific and wide optical range of Finnish waters. Therefore, the lakes have been grouped to optical classes that define the conversion factors between IOPs and water quality parameters. The lake grouping was done on the basis of optical classification and Hydrolight simulations based on station measurements (Figure 15) and moderated to four to six final classes depending on the water quality parameter.

Figure 15 Typical Rrs of WFD water body types of Finnish lakes. The water body types are grouped according to humic substance (CDOM) concentration into following classes a) low b) moderate and c) high humic level. The last group also includes eutrophic water body type (yellow spectrum). Rrs were simulated by Hydrolight using measured median TSM, Chl-*a* and *a*CDOM of the water bodies. Dashed spectrum is the median Rrs of all water body types. The original dataset included measurements from 2 832 water bodies. Fixed Y-axis range

Product details

- Turbidity and a_{CDOM} are estimated using C2RCC processor (chapter V.3.) IOPs detritus absorption (*adet*) and total scattering (*btot*), respectively. Secchi depth is defined based on the conversion using the C2RCC processor output *kd_z90max*. The optical water groups (Figure 15 and Figure 16) define the coefficients used in the the water quality algorithms based on the outcomes C2RCC. (TSM is not regularly measured in Finnish sampling stations.) During the algorithm development phase other algorithms such as band ratios using Polymer or C2RCC processor reflectance outputs were also examined. The current approach was found the most suitable for the whole lakes district and coastal waters.

Figure 16 An example of Finnish lakes district divided to classes defining the optical water types. The colors represent different optical groups of lakes. The optical water groups define the coefficients used in the the water quality algorithms based on the outcomes C2RCC.

- Classification for turbidity algorithm
 - Lakes with very low turbidity
 - Moderate turbidity and low aCDOM
 - Moderate turbidity and high in aCDOM
 - Very turbid lakes
- The equations for turbidity are of the form
$$\text{Turbidity} = a_1 * iop_btot^{a_2} + a_0;$$
- Secchi disk depth and a_{CDOM} algorithms are formulated using the same principle as turbidity but with specific coefficients and limits within optical grouping.
- Algae bloom estimation maps are based on four classes: no algae, potential, likely and evident surface floating algae blooms. The maps are using S3-OLCI, S2-MSI and LC8-OLI observations. The algae products are formulated based on thresholds for reflectances at chosen bands (depending on the instrument) and filtering the output to reach a generalized algae bloom class map.
- The lower limit of water body area is approx. 0.5 km² (as according to the WFD).
- Shallow waters are excluded using depth raster map covering the lakes and coastal waters.
- Lakes with mean depth less than 3m are excluded.
- In total, about 2500 lakes are included in water body statistics products.
- The estimates of turbidity, Secchi depth and a_{CDOM} algorithms are fitted to uniform level for LC8-OLI and S2-MSI instruments.
- SST Sentinel-3 SLSTR products are generated with the standard algorithm (L1 product) complemented with SYKE cloud buffering and land masking. SYKE uses only morning and evening overpasses.
- For all products except SST, cloud masking is based on Idepix, complemented with SYKE cloud shadow detection algorithm with additional buffering of clouds and cloud shadows. Cloud shadow detection algorithm uses sun angle and a locally estimated (iterated) cloud height to detect the area shadowed by the cloud.

Figure 17 a) Coastal turbidity image product (S2-MSI) 16.9.2018.b) Algae bloom estimation (OLCI) 16.7.2018

Figure 18 Water body statistics, histograms and time series products for WFD water bodies

Figure 19 Reference station time series product of turbidity [FNU] (Lake Tuusulanjärvi). Dots represent turbidity estimates using LC8, S2A and S2B instruments. Red triangle is the analysed station observation

The EOMORES product *Spatial representativeness analysis based on EO data* is applied by the end user in a service build for forecasting and assessing water bodies' ecological status that is based on data fusion methods. This EOMORES product is used in the parametrization of the applied data fusion algorithms. The spatial representativeness analysis is based on the geostatistical variogram methods (formalized in Matheron (1963) and explained in e.g. Burrough and McDonnel (1998) and in Ford (2018)) on MERIS data originated chlorophyll *a* and turbidity estimations and further, on the fitting of the most suitable variogram models for the observed distance depended variance. Analysis was performed for the two pilot areas (combination of two coastal water bodies in the Southern coast of Finland and Lake Pyhäjärvi) by applying and combining all available EO based observations from seasons 2009 and 2011.

Figure 20. Examples on the variogram models fitted on the observed chlorophyll *a* (MERIS) semivariances from the coastal site (7.7.2017; left figure) and on the turbidity based semivariances from Lake Pyhäjärvi (21.6.2009; right figure)

VIII.3. Italy

MSI-S2A/B L1C images were resampled at 10 m through SNAP *S2-toolbox*, with nearest neighbour method, and TOA reflectances $\rho_{toa}(\lambda)$ were converted into $L_{toa}(\lambda)$ before being ingested by the interface used for atmospheric correction, according the following equation:

$$L_{toa}(\lambda) = \frac{\rho_{toa}(\lambda) F_0(\lambda) U \cos(\theta)}{\pi}$$

where $F_0(\lambda)$ is the extra-terrestrial solar irradiance for each band λ , U is the correction factor taking into account Earth-Sun distance variation, and θ is the solar zenith angle over each target pixel, as provided in L1C products file metadata. From this point on images processing was done following different methods depending on the parameter to be estimated.

Based on the characteristics of the lakes considered and on the users' requests concerning the different water quality parameters, different processes are used to obtain water quality products. For the estimation of the Chl-a and TSM in the deep oligo/mesotrophic subalpine lakes (Lake Garda, Como, Lake Iseo, Oggiono) and for the Lake Trasimeno, for all the images (OLCI, MSI, OLI), an approach combined between 6SV (excellent results were obtained with the polymer) and BOMBER bio-optical model. The possibility of using the C2RCC with the specific IOP of the individual lakes considered is being analyzed. For the discrimination and spatial quantification of the superficial blooms of cyanobacteria from OLCI images, the images corrected with 6SV are analyzed among band-ratio based on the spectral features determined by the secondary pigments of cyanobacteria. To obtain the Water (Z90) products in Lake Trasimeno, the estimation was performed with CC2R adapted with regional tuning. For the Lake Mezzola, being the request of the user focused only on the estimation of turbidity, and being the lake is characterized by high turbidity, ACOLITE was used.

To produce coverage maps and health status of the emerged aquatic vegetation of Lake Oggiono, the MSI images are corrected with the 6SV and spectral vegetation indices are applied (Villa et al., 2016); while for the submerged macrophytes of Iseo lake to the MSI images corrected with the 6SV was applied the bio-optical BOMBER model in shallow lake mode (Giardino et al., 2007).

- Chl-a and TSM: the atmospheric correction was carried out using 6SV code through an interface realised by CNR-IREA to include as input to 6SV code also microphysical properties of aerosols, as provided by AERONET network, and specific sensors SRFs. In case of lakes nearby AERONET sites (e.g. Garda), AERONET level1.5 values of Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT), columnar ozone concentration and columnar water content were used to parametrize the 6SV. In addition, AERONET inversion products, complex refractive index and particle size distribution, were used, when synchronous (within a ± 3 hours interval); otherwise, if not available, their seasonal mean spectrum was used. AOT at 550 nm was retrieved through exponential interpolation of available values along spectrum and with weighted averaged between the two closest measurements in time. When not even AERONET direct products were available, AOT at 550 nm and water vapour values were retrieved from daily MODIS products, via NASA Giovanni interface (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>) and OMI-Aura (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) products were used for Ozone concentration. Water leaving reflectance ρ_w was obtained from radiance at Top of Atmosphere L_{toa} as in Eq. xx, for each band λ , where the three coefficients $x_a(\lambda)$, $x_b(\lambda)$, and $x_c(\lambda)$ are 6SV simulation output.

$$\rho_w(\lambda) = \frac{L_{toa}(\lambda) x_a(\lambda) - x_b(\lambda)}{1 + x_c(\lambda) (L_{toa}(\lambda) x_a(\lambda) - x_b(\lambda))}$$

The 6SV-derived atmospherically corrected ρ_w was then converted into Rrs above water dividing it by π . A bio-optical model was then applied on Rrs products to obtain chl-a concentrations maps: BOMBER (Bio-Optical Model-Based tool for Estimating water quality and bottom properties from Remote sensing images (Giardino et al. 2012). BOMBER is a four-component model developed to determine water constituents in optically complex waters through a spectral inversion procedure. In this study, the model, was parametrized using site specific Inherent Optical Properties IOPs gathered in situ. Example of chl-a products is given in Figure 21.

Figure 21 Chl-a maps form S2 and L8 in subalpine lakes of Lombardia region observed in 2016

- Turbidity: the processing based on ACOLITE, by using the Nechad algorithm. The oldest version of this processor (Vanhellemont and Ruddick, 2014, 2015, 2016) was used to process the first year images simultaneous to field campaigns. These images were then reprocessed through the latest version ('Python 'public beta' 20180419.0'), but results were kept and compared. This latest version allows performing atmospheric correction, in addition to the previous method, with the Dark Spectrum Fitting (DSF) algorithm (Vanhellemont and Ruddick, submitted) as a default and recommended by authors.
- Water transparency (Z90), the estimation was performed with C2RCC adapted with regional tuning.
- LSWT: Sentinel-3 SLSTR data the level2 products were used.
- Emerged macrophytes: Vegetation indexes (Villa et al. 2015; Villa et al., 2018)
- Submerged vegetation: Inversion of Bio-optical model Bomber (Giardino et al., 2012)

VIII.4. Lithuania

MODIS Terra/Aqua Level 2 daytime (MODIS thermal bands 31 (11 μ) and 32 (12 μ) imagery (L2_LAC_SST product) covering the coastal waters of SE Baltic Sea and the Curonian Lagoon with spatial resolution of about 1 km were obtained from the NASA OceanColor website (<http://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). A standard MODIS cloud mask encrypted in the Level-2 flags was used to eliminate cloud-contaminated pixels. Images were reprojected to UTM – WGS84 Zone 34N.

In case of the Curonian Lagoon thematic maps of Chl-a, cyanobacteria accumulation, TSM and WST maps were produced to users:

- Chl-a: the atmospheric correction was carried out using 6SV code through an interface realised by CNR-IREA (cf. Figure 3). In case of the Curonian Lagoon, Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT) values were gathered from AERONET website (https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/new_web/index.html). AOT level2.0 from Gustav_Dalen_Tower Site located in the Baltic Sea close to Sweden or AOT at 550 nm and water vapour values retrieved from daily MODIS products, via NASA Giovanni interface (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>) were used to parametrize the 6SV. As an output Water leaving reflectance ρ_w was obtained from radiance at Top of Atmosphere L_{toa} . To obtain Rrs, atmospherically corrected ρ_w was divided by π . Chl-a concentration was produced (an example in Figure 22) after the application of semi-empirical band-ratio model that use the reflectance in the red and near-infrared (NIR) spectral regions. Different equations were used for MSI and OLCI as indicated in INFORM D5.15 (INFORM, 2016):

$$Chl - a (mg m^{-3}) = 78 \times \left(\frac{Ref_{705}}{Ref_{665}} \right) - 51.2$$

$$Chl - a (mg m^{-3}) = 52.19 \times \left(\frac{Ref_{708}}{Ref_{665}} \right) - 32.07$$

- TSM: the processing of MSI and OLI are based on ACOLITE (version 20170718.0 for Windows), by using the Nechad algorithm (Nechad2016, 865 nm band) (Nechad et al., 2010).

- Water Surface Temperature (WST): MODIS/Aqua, MODIS/Terra data the L2 products were used.

Figure 22 Monthly means of Chl-a in the Curonian Lagoon in 2017

- In case of the coastal waters of the SE Baltic Sea, thematic maps of SST maps were produced to users. MODIS/Aqua, MODIS/Terra data the L2 products were used. Currently C2RCC processor available within the SNAP processing toolbox is being tested to retrieve three water quality components: Chl-a, TSM and CDOM.

VIII.5. The Netherlands

TripleSat VHR imagery were downloaded from the Dutch Satellite data portal (www.satellietbeeld.nl)

WorldView VHR imagery was requested from the Data Ware House and downloaded from the ESA cds sso portal

VIII.5.1. Lake Markermeer

What

- S2 and S3 for water quality parameters.
- L8 for a few temperature examples
- Report delivered with analysis and maps, no data.

S2 and S3

- Atmospheric correction: C2RCC was used for both S2 and S3
- Chl-a: Gons et al. (2005), setting all concentrations between 0 and 1 to 1

- SPM: Nechad et al. (2010) based on band 705, but multiplied with 1.4. This multiplication was found to lead to the best concentrations of validation data sets
- SD: based on a combination of Alikas and Kratzer. First, K_d is calculated according to Alikas et al. (2015), using the turbid water ratio ($\rho(560)/\rho(709)$). Next, the Secchi disk depth is calculated according to Alikas and Kratzer (2017), using the Himmelfjorden parameterisation.
- Monthly aggregates of Chl, SPM and Secchi were made using SNAP
-

Figure 23, Example of a map of the MarkerWadden area in lake Markermeer

L8

- Digital numbers were converted to spectral radiance (Landsat 8 manual <https://landsat.usgs.gov/landsat-8-data-users-handbook>)
- Atmospheric correction: Barsi (2005) using $L_t = (L_{toa} - L_u - \tau * (1 - \epsilon) * L_d) / (\tau * \epsilon)$. For emissivity ϵ , a constant value of 0.99 was used. For each image, the required τ , L_u and L_d were obtained from the NASA atmospheric correction web tool (<https://atmcorr.gsfc.nasa.gov/>) and local surface conditions from KNMI (http://www.sciamachy-validation.org/climatology/daily_data/selection.cgi)
- Calculated surface temperature according to the temperature equations as provided in the L8 manual (<https://landsat.usgs.gov/landsat-8-data-users-handbook>), but at surface level instead, using band 10.

VIII.5.2. Lake Lauwersmeer and channels in surrounding area

What

- S2 for Chl (only for the lake)
- VHR imagery (tests with both TripleSat and WorldView) for tracing locations with plants
- Data files delivery in requested format
- Maps for visualisation

S2:

- Atmospheric correction: Rayleigh correction in SNAP
- Chl-a : Gons (2005), setting all concentrations between 0 and 1 to 1
- Boat removal based on Top of Atmosphere band 8
- Data files delivered in FEWS compatible format (ascii)
- Maps of concentrations (.png)

TripleSat

- True colour and false colour composites provided as maps

WorldView 2 and/or 3:

- Extract water surface using shape files
- NDVI to trace above water vegetation
- Differentiation between Duck weed and scum versus other floating plants, and submerged vegetation based on spectral shapes e.g in the blue wavelenths (*under developement*)

VIII.5.3. Lake Paterswoldsemeer

What

- S2 for water quality parameters (Chl-a and SPM)
- VHR imagery (tests with both TripleSat and WorldView) for tracing locations with plants
- Data files delivery in requested format (only for S2 based products)
- Maps for visualisation

S2:

- Atmospheric correction: forced based on EcoWatch in situ reflectances
- Land flag: Top of Atmosphere band > 0.1
- Boat removal based on Top of Atmosphere band 8
- Chl-a: Gons, using a fixed bb value of 0.01. Set all concentrations between 0 and 1 to 1, remove negative values,
- SPM: Nechad (2010) based on band 705
- Data files delivered in FEWS compatible format (ascii)
- Maps of concentrations (.png)

Figure 24 Examples of maps of lake Paterswoldsemeer

WorldView 2 and/or 3:

- Extract water surface using shape files
- NDVI to trace above water vegetation
- Differentiation between Duck weed and scum versus other floating plants, and submerged vegetation based on spectral shapes e.g in the blue wavelenths (*under development*)

VIII.5.4. Pond in 'Park van Luna', Lake Geesterambacht, Lake Alkmaardermeer and channels in the same area

What

- VHR imagery (tests with both TripleSat and WorldView) for tracing locations with plants

TripleSat (only for pond in Park van Luna and channels in the same area):

- True colour and false colour composites provided as maps

WorldView 2 and/or 3:

- Extract water surface using shape files
- NDVI to trace above water vegetation
- Differentiation between Duck weed and scum versus other floating plants, and submerged vegetation based on spectral shapes e.g in the blue wavelenths (*under development*)

VIII.6. United Kingdom

For the UK and Ireland, MSI-S2A data are automatically downloaded from the Copernicus hub and processed using the Calimnos software. This is an extended satellite processing chain originally intended to deal with the optical complexity, variability and wide spatial distribution of global inland water bodies. Calimnos utilizes a range of published and validated algorithms for the retrieval of water quality parameters (Chl-a, TSM, CDOM, phycocyanin). Each of the algorithms was developed to handle a relatively narrow range of conditions (e.g. clear or eutrophic waters) and should therefore not be equally used between waterbodies or in all seasons. Calimnos dynamically applies the most suitable algorithms to satellite observations depending on the similarity of the atmospherically corrected reflectance spectrum to established optical water types. For inland waters, the types are derived from a large in situ data set as described in Spyarakos et al. (2017). Depending on the availability of in situ concentration data matching a satellite observation, the individual algorithms have also been tuned by the University of Stirling to the widest possible data set for each optical water body, often combining measurements from multiple regions in the world and thereby avoiding geographical or methodological bias.

The main benefits of using an optical water type (OWT) approach to mapping optical-biogeochemical variables in any water body include (1) avoiding use of any individual retrieval algorithm outside of its calibrated scope; (2) calibration of the algorithms using the global archive of in situ matchups sharing an OWT, rather than from an individual water body; (3) dynamic assignment of algorithms for each pixel and observation in time, thus avoiding seasonal bias that could occur when applying a single algorithm across OWTs; (4) traceability of OWT similarity scores, allowing pixels with an uncertain or unknown OWT to be flagged during processing. These advantages are of particular importance when applying the OWT framework to regions where in situ reference data are scarce or far apart: water-leaving reflectance spectra that are similar to known OWTs can be interpreted with confidence using algorithms from other regions in the world, while product uncertainty can be traced back to areas with previously uncharacterized OWTs, so that in situ calibration and validation activities can focus their efforts there.

The published methods implemented in Calimnos are:

Chl-a:

- Gons et al. 2005.
- OC2E v6 algorithm
- Gilerson et al (2010)
- Mishra et al. 2013

TSM and turbidity:

- Nechad et al. 2010, algorithm applied to one of 665nm, 705nm, 783nm, 865nm bands
- Binding et al. 2010
- Zhang et al. 2014
- Vantrepotte et al. 2011

CDOM:

- Mishra et al. 2013
- Ficek et al. 2011

Phycocyanin:

- Simis et al. 2007
- Mishra et al. 2013
- Liu et al. 2017

Figure 25 Optical water types (a) and turbidity (b,c) derived from an MSI scene over Cumbria, UK

Although all algorithms are fully implemented within the Calimnos processing chain, further validation is required for the values derived from MSI and OLCI data.

IX. Conclusions

Most of the challenges in inland and coastal water observations are due to their optical complexity. These aquatic ecosystems can be a mixture of optically shallow and optically deep waters, with gradients of clear to turbid and oligotrophic to hypertrophic productive waters and varying bottom visibility with and without macrophytes. For example, a lake receives and recycles organic and inorganic substances from within the lake, from its watershed and beyond (atmospheric deposition). Hence, a large range in optical absorption and backscattering resulting in high optical variability can be found among and within lakes, estuaries and coastal waters. This poses a challenge for bio-optical algorithms applied to optical remote sensing for water quality monitoring applications. Another challenge is performing atmospheric corrections over such variable aquatic ecosystems as their complexity requires different approaches than those for land and ocean applications.

Within EOMORES the state-of-the-art of remote sensing of lakes is used to generate water quality products in a variety of ecosystems, from deep clear lakes, to eutrophic brackish waters, to CDOM-rich lakes. Maps of chl-a are the best example of the EO processors adopted in EMORES as they have been generated for almost for every target area and for multiple years. Most of the activities have been based on Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel 3 OLCI data, although other data from other satellite missions (e.g. Landsat, MODIS) have been included. Although the use of optical data might be hindered by cloud cover these imagery have offered unprecedented data for timely, frequent, synoptic measurement of EOMORES lakes. The EO measure acquired also in other wavelengths, rather than the VIS-NIR, of the electromagnetic spectrum have been investigated such as the thermal infrared for mapping surface water temperature, and radar for its possibility to detect scum (at least in very eutrophic waters) in case of clouds.

X. References

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